

IEA Wind Task 52 Meeting Minutes

IEA Wind Task 52 General Meeting 2025

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IEA Wind Task 52 is part of the International Energy Agency (IEA) Technology Collaboration Programme (TCP) Wind and aims at making wind lidar the preferred wind measurement tool for wind energy applications, facilitating the large-scale deployment of wind energy.

The Task 52 General Meeting was held on September 23-24, 2025 at Fraunhofer IEE, Joseph-Beuys-Straße 8, 34117 Kassel. The meeting focused on providing updates regarding the current status of wind lidar technology, the progress of Task 52 working groups, and developments since the last General Meeting in 2024. Task 52 was positioned as an evolution of Task 32, transitioning from a focus on “single-lidar technology” to “multiple lidars and their emerging use cases,” with a stronger emphasis on user involvement and the evidence required for developing standards. Another key focus was the preparation for a potential Phase 2 (spanning four years), which is contingent on gathering sufficient evidence and securing stakeholder commitment by the end of Phase 1. The meeting included several presentations on the progress of the working groups and breakout sessions addressing challenges related to IEA Wind Task 52.

Contents

1 Day 1: Tuesday 23 September 2025	1
1.1 Welcome and introduction by OA . . .	1
1.2 Agenda - Day 1	2
1.3 Welcome by host (Fraunhofer IEE, Kassel)	2
1.4 Guidance on timeline and next steps (OA)	2
1.5 Short overview of working groups (high-level)	2
1.6 Technical presentations — focus on academic (10:45–12:30)	3
1.7 Industry Perspective (13:30–14:45) . .	6
1.8 Breakouts matchmaking & answers to questions captured on the whiteboards	6
1.9 Various presentations (15:30–17:00) . .	6
2 Day 2: Wednesday 24 September 2025	8
2.1 Agenda - Day 2	8
2.2 Presentations + panel: OEMs on challenges (and further opportunities) . . .	8

2.3 Results of complex terrain working group and “What’s next”	9
2.4 Breakouts	9
2.5 Workshops	10
3 Summary	11

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The presence of a person’s name or company name in this document should not be taken to imply that a person or their employer agrees with any of the opinions set out here.

1 Day 1: Tuesday 23 September 2025

1.1 Welcome and introduction by OA

The day started with a welcome and introduction by Julia Gottschall, the Operating Agent (OA) of Task 52.

Julia Gottschall (OA) set the context for the General Meeting and for the final Task year. After presenting the agenda, she reflected on the lineage of lidar activities within the IEA Wind community—recalling the first topical expert meeting in 2007 that culminated in the Remote Sensing Recommended Practices—and noted that foundational themes such as turbulence remain central today. She then situated Task 52 as the evolution of Task 32: expanding from “single-lidar technology” to “multiple lidars and their emerging use cases,” with stronger emphasis on user involvement and evidence needed for standards. The four Themes and associated working groups were introduced, with further detail scheduled later in the programme. Additionally, participant details were provided, along with avenues for staying informed and connected with the task through various links, including references to the website <https://iea-wind.org/task52/>, the Zenodo community <https://zenodo.org/communities/ieawindtask52>, the LinkedIn profile <https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/4037465/>, and the mailing list IEAWind.Task52@iwes.fraunhofer.de.

End-of-Phase-1 focus. The OA emphasised that we are approaching the end of Phase 1 and that 2025–26 activities must converge on documented, citable out-

puts (e.g., expert notes, RP inputs, datasets) that directly support standardisation and bankability across onshore and offshore applications. (See §1.4.)

1.2 Agenda - Day 1

Time	Activity
09:00	Welcome by host
09:15	Welcome and overview of Task 52 from Operating Agent (OA), including short overview of working groups <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Richard Frühmann (DNV): "WG1 - Turbulence Intensity (TI)" Sara Koller (Meteotest AG): "WG4 - Cold Climate" Andy Clifton (Enerlace GmbH): "WG5 - Digitalisation" Andy Oldroyd (Oldbaum Services): "WG6 - Scanning Lidar (Recommended Practices)" Okan Sargin (Fraunhofer IWES): "WG9 - Floating LiDAR"
10:45	Coffee, Tea
11:00	Technical presentations - focus on academic advancements (chair: Doron Callies) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Kira Gramitzky (Fraunhofer IEE): "An extension of the Sea Surface Levelling method for determining the alignment accuracy of offshore scanning lidars" Elliot Simon (DTU): "FLOW Campaign - Multi-lidar coherence measurements of offshore turbulent inflows" Martin Hofsäß (SWE): "Evolution of the SWE Research Lidar Scanner" Lin-Ya Hung (Fraunhofer IWES): "Measuring Offshore Wakes with Nacelle-Scanning Lidars: New Scan Strategy and Key Insights" Sam Cressall (Edinburgh University): "Impact of TI measurement uncertainty on AEP"
12:30	Lunch + Lab visit (IEE) + Group photo
13:30	Industry perspective (chair: Sara Koller) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Jun Tanemoto (Shimizu Corporation): "Lidar Deployment Acceleration by Research in Japan" Dirk Steudel (Nordex): "KPIs for Lidar TI" Euan MacDonald (ZX Lidars): "Latest TI developments" Christoph Bollig (Abacus Laser): "Long range scanning wind lidar beyond 25 km range: Current status and future perspectives" Giannis Kissas (2en): "Lidar in Wind Energy: Industry Perspectives, Challenges and Opportunities"
15:45	Breakouts / Matchmaking
16:30	Various presentations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Okan Sargin (Fraunhofer IWES): "Review of WESC 2025 mini-symposium" Stefano Letizia (NREL): "Summary of NAWEA 2024 side event" Andrew Black (Vaisala): "Simple+ terrain" Andy Oldroyd (Oldbaum): "Lidars and beyond"
17:00	Wrap-up of Day 1

Table 1: Agenda of Day 1.

Theme	Working group (active)
#1 Universal inflow characterisation	(#1) Turbulence Intensity (TI) by Lidar (#2) Lidar Assisted Control (LAC)
#2 Replacing met masts	(#3) Lidar in Complex Terrain (#4) Lidar in Cold Climate (#8) Nacelle Mounted Lidar in Complex Terrain (NML-X)
#3 Connecting wind lidar	(#5) Digitalization (#7) Lidar Ontology
#4 Accelerating offshore wind deployment	(#6) Scanning Lidar Offshore (#9) Floating LiDAR

Table 2: Working groups of Task 52.

1.3 Welcome by host (Fraunhofer IEE, Kassel)

The meeting opened at Fraunhofer IEE with words of welcome and practical information. Prof. Martin Braun (Institutsleiter, Fraunhofer IEE) briefly introduced the host institute's mission and the relevance of lidar-enabled wind-energy research to the region and to Germany's energy transition. The day's timings followed the circulated agenda.

1.4 Guidance on timeline and next steps (OA)

Using the timeline slide, the OA reiterated:

- Phase 1 start:** 1 June 2022; **all Phase 1 deliverables due:** 31 May 2026.
- Working groups:** formed to deliver against the four Themes, with cross-WG alignment on terminology and uncertainty treatment.
- Outlook:** preparation for a **possible Phase 2 (four years)**, contingent on evidence and stakeholder commitment assembled by end-Phase-1.

This guidance framed the morning's short working-group snapshots and the later technical sessions (academic focus before lunch; industry perspective in the afternoon).

1.5 Short overview of working groups (high-level)

The OA provided concise status notes to orient participants ahead of detailed updates:

WG1 - Turbulence Intensity (TI) —Richard Frühmann (DNV)

The group is consolidating evidence on how lidar-derived TI should be adapted or interpreted for core applications—yield assessment, power performance, loads, and lifetime—and is mapping where TI sits in the IEC 61400-12/-50 series. Work in 2025 centres on a structured literature review and a draft recommenda-

tion that clarifies methods for comparing lidar derived TI with a suitable reference, with regular meetings sustaining momentum toward end-of-Task outputs.

WG4 Cold Climate —Sara Koller (Meteotest AG)

WG4 is addressing two practical questions: (i) why lidar data availability drops in cold climates and how it can be increased, and (ii) whether and how lidars can support meteorological icing detection, potentially informing “ice classes.” The group plans a short synthesis report that captures Task-period findings by May 2026; a hands-on workshop during the GM advances the methodological detail.

WG5 - Digitalisation —Andy Clifton (Enerlace GmbH)

The digitalisation effort focuses on business cases, interoperability, and demonstrators (ontology and e-WindLidar workflows). The headline lesson from 2022–25 is that today’s blockers are mostly commercial and organisational — and *not* specific to wind lidar — and that providing clearer ROI arguments is decisive. A report summarising the use cases for digitalisation of wind lidar is planned for Q4 2025 to document what works and where value is created.

WG6 - Scanning Lidar (Recommended Practices) — Andy Oldroyd (Oldbaum services)

WG6 is building the evidence base for an RP that supports IEC 61400-50-5. Three Datathons underpin the work: Datathon-1 on sub-10-minute availability (Recovery Rate), Datathon-2 on uncertainty (now entering Phase-2 to connect LOS to reconstructed wind-field uncertainty), and Datathon-3 on hard-targeting methods and their relative accuracies. The next steps are to collate results, identify residual gaps, and begin drafting the RP text.

WG9 - Floating LiDAR (launched 2025) — Leads: Julia Gottschall; Okan Sargin (Fraunhofer IWES).

WG9 is aiming alignment with IEC 61400-50-4 and concentrates on five objectives: TRL/bankability of Stage-3 FLS, data-quality thresholds, campaign design, technology/ML application, and uncertainty benchmarking aligned with IEC 61400-50-4. The plan is monthly online sessions leading to concise documents and an open review window, with dissemination targeted for Mar–Apr 2026.

These short snapshots were presented to frame the deeper technical blocks later in the agenda and to keep participants focused on end-of-Phase-1, citable deliverables.

Break (10:45). Coffee tea as per agenda before the technical presentations block.

1.6 Technical presentations — focus on academic (10:45–12:30)

This session showcased current academic work that underpins Task 52’s end-of-Phase-1 deliverables and standardisation inputs. The Operating Agent reiterated that evidence from these talks should flow directly into WG outputs (expert notes, RP text, datasets) and help align terminology and uncertainty treatment across themes. Following presentations were held which are discussed in subsequent sections:

- [Kira Gramitzky \(Fraunhofer IEE\): “An extension of the Sea Surface Levelling method for determining the alignment accuracy of offshore scanning lidars”](#)
- [Elliot Simon \(DTU\): “FLOW Campaign - Multi-lidar coherence measurements of offshore turbulent inflows”](#)
- [Martin Hofsäß \(SWE\): “Evolution of the SWE Research Lidar Scanner”](#)
- [Lin-Ya Hung \(Fraunhofer IWES\): “Measuring Offshore Wakes with Nacelle-Scanning Lidars: New Scan Strategy and Key Insights”](#)
- [Sam Cressall \(Edinburgh University\): “Impact of TI measurement uncertainty on AEP”](#)

1.6.1 Extending Sea Surface Levelling (SSL) for offshore scanning-lidar alignment

Presenter / affiliation: Kira Gramitzky (Fraunhofer IEE; Univ. Kassel)

Summary: The talk generalised SSL to retrieve pitch, roll and elevation offset for offshore scanning lidars, independent of scan pattern and including Earth curvature. Sensitivity to range bias and sea state was explored, with practical guidance on distance determination (e.g. CNR inflection-point fitting).

Key scientific points:

- **Method/data:** Extended SSL formulation; sector scans; repeated RHIs under low-to-moderate wind and wave conditions.
- **Findings:** Pitch/roll stable within a few hundredths of a degree; elevation offset robust but sensitive to systematic range bias; wave effects small in the cases tested.
- **Limitations:** At very high wind and wave states, platform motions may degrade SSL robustness; careful treatment of distance bias is required.

Discussion and clarifications (Q&A excerpts):

- **Applicability in high sea states:** SSL performance may be reduced under “really high wind waves” due to platform motion; one root cause is motion-induced errors that the standard SSL workflow does not fully capture.
- **Inclination/tilt knowledge:** For live turbines, knowledge of device inclination (via inclinometer) is required; the inclinometer should be calibrated for absolute tilt.
- **Inclinometer accuracy:** Technical specification exist, but turbine tilt can “prevail” in the signal. A 30-s mean tilt on monopiles was cited; some averaging is needed and the signal is not perfectly correlated with true inclination—averaging intervals >30s up to 10 min are suitable for beam correction of scanning lidars mounted on the transition pieces of monopile-founded turbines. Good agreement with reference Nacelle-mounted lidar (NML) measurement in an offshore.
- **RHI vs PPI cross-check:** PPI was used as an independent check, comparable results to RHI settings.
- **Time synchronisation:** RHI accumulation and the inclinometer ran on different time frames; RHI accumulation over 25 minutes, high-frequency inclinometer averaged over 10 minutes.

Relevance to Task 52/WGs: WG6 (Offshore Scanning Lidar RP: alignment/QA) and WG5 (metadata and uncertainty patterns).

Further reference: <https://wes.copernicus.org/preprints/wes-2025-191/>

1.6.2 FLOW campaign: multi-lidar coherence of offshore turbulent inflow

Presenter / affiliation: Elliot Simon (DTU Wind Energy)

Summary: Multi-lidar lateral-coherence nearshore wind measurements at 150–250 m ASL using mixed systems (DTU WindScanners, Lumibird XR+, WindCube 200S). The campaign data was used to validate an improved low-frequency anisotropic turbulence model [1]. The campaign employed RHI-based SSL scans and drone-based beam alignment both pre- and post-campaign to improve pointing accuracy. The dataset is publicly available [2].

Key scientific points:

- **Methods/results:** Lidars in staring mode (2 Hz); six crossing points with 2-component retrieval; coherence vs separation matched model behaviour in unstable regimes; strong QC via hard-targets and drone alignment.
- **Caveats:** Coherence appears noisy at times; influenced by atmospheric conditions and lidar signal quality (CNR).

Discussion and clarifications (Q&A excerpts):

- **Coherence noisiness:** Acknowledged; further information on filtering and interpretation will be documented in upcoming paper in Wind Energy Science [3].
- **Range-gate settings:** Shortest pulse length setting was used to minimize the probe volume for turbulence measurements. 80 ns on Lumibird units and 100 ns used on WindScanners and Windcubes.
- **Drone platform and positioning:** DJI Matrice 600 Pro RTK was used, achieving RMS positioning accuracy on the order of centimetres. Remaining uncertainty stems from where along the drone the beam is intersected; overlapping-hit strategies reduce this. Details on the drone alignment method are described in [4]. Journal article is being prepared for submission in 2026 [5].
- **IEC turbulence models:** The goal is to assess how well industry-standard (IEC-approved) models capture turbulence conditions at higher heights where turbines are now operating. Also to develop existing and new turbulence models and validate them against the observations collected here. Conclusions are forthcoming as part of a multi-year project (first stage presented here).
- **Operational constraints:** Graph origin “0 km” marks the lidar; practical visual tracking becomes difficult above 1 km range and in strong/turbulent winds where the drone struggles to hold position. The drone method was successfully used on all lidars to minimize uncertainty due to pointing errors.

Relevance to Task 52/WGs: WG1 (TI from lidar), WG6 (offshore scanning validation), WG5 (ontology mapping of shared dataset).

Further references:

- [1] Syed, A. H., Mann, J. (2024). A Model for Low-Frequency, Anisotropic Wind Fluctuations and Coherences in the Marine Atmosphere. *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, 190, Article 1. [Link](#)
- [2] Patel, Ansh; Simon, Elliot; Mann, Jakob; Sjöholm, Mikael; Rolighed Thorsen, Gunhild; Hung, Lin-Ya; et al. (2025). *Trans experiment (FLOW) - raw lidar data*. Technical University of Denmark. Dataset: [Link](#)
- [3] Mann, Jakob; Patel, Ansh; Sjöholm, Mikael; Thorsen, Gunhild; Simon, Elliot; Hung, Lin-Ya; Gottschall, Julia (Expected submission December 2025). *An experimental campaign to measure turbulence in the marine boundary layer*. [4] Thorsen, G. R., Simon, E., Clausen, E. H. (2023). *Drone-based scanning lidar pointing calibration (D4.4)*. DTU Wind and Energy Systems. [Link](#)
- [5] Thorsen, Gunhild; Simon, Elliot; Hung, Lin-Ya; Gottschall, Julia (Expected submission 2026). *Using Drone Hard-Targeting for Improved Scanning Wind Lidar Beam Pointing Accuracy*.

1.6.3 Evolution of the SWE research scanning lidar (towards offshore 2.1)

Presenter / affiliation: Martin Hofstätter (Stuttgart Wind Energy, Institute of Aircraft Design, University of Stuttgart).

Summary: SWE outlined the progression from its

first nacelle-based scanning lidar to a compact Scanner 2.0 and an offshore-oriented Scanner 2.1, emphasising flexible, user-defined scan trajectories for Lidar-Assisted Control (LAC), power-curve work, and multi-sensor wind-field measurements.

Conclusion: Scanner 2.0 is a deployable research platform; Scanner 2.1 targets offshore robustness and reliability for floating applications and is advancing through field activities (WINSENT, NEOWIND, ABBA, EMUwind).

Key scientific points:

- **Methods/results:**
 - Early system (1.0) with 2-DOF mirror and Wind-Cube V1 enabled the CART2 LAC proof-of-concept, reducing generator-speed variation.
 - Scanner 2.0 specifications: 350 × 620 mm, 45 kg, 24 V DC (80 W); 45–885 m range (environment-dependent), up to 59 planes, ±26.6° azimuth/elevation; fast, user-defined trajectories.
 - Scanner 2.1 (under development) keeps scan flexibility while aiming for >30 kg and higher MTBF for harsh offshore and floating conditions.
- **Caveats:** Pre-calibration WINSENT comparisons are marked “not calibrated, preliminary”; Scanner 2.1 values are targets pending validation; effective range depends on conditions.

Discussion and clarifications (Q&A excerpts):

- No discussion captured in session notes

Relevance to Task 52/WGs: WG1, WG2, WG3, WG5, WG6, WG8, WG9

1.6.4 Measuring offshore wakes with nacelle-scanning lidars: new scan strategy & insights

Presenter / affiliation: Lin-Ya (Lilian) Hung (Fraunhofer IWES)

Summary: Three nacelle-mounted scanning lidars executed 90° PPI scans (90 s per scan) to quantify near/far wakes and wake superposition across adjacent wind-farm technologies. A motion-compensated coordinate workflow and static common grid were developed for inter-lidar comparison.

Conclusion: We present a nacelle-mounted, scanning lidar system for wind-turbine wake measurements, highlighting practical considerations and data insights. A verification case using two scanning lidars evaluates the setup’s accuracy and examines sources of error.

Key scientific points:

- **Methods/results:** GNSS + motion sensors; adaptive scans; local-to-UTM transforms; vector projection; 30-min hub-height comparisons yielded RMSE 0.7 m s⁻¹ and MBE 0.2 m s⁻¹.
- **Caveats:** Co-locality, motion compensation and interpolation drive the uncertainty; robust operations/logging are essential offshore.

Discussion and clarifications (Q&A excerpts):

- **R² question:** A request was raised to clarify which R² is being reported, it was (lidar downstream reprojected LoS) v.s. (lidar upstream reprojected LoS)
- **Placement/blockage/rotor filtering:** Beam blockage and rotor-related filtering issues were surprisingly low in the presented configuration.
- **Overlapping-area retrieval:** Overlap between systems existed but the scans were not time-coordinated; whole-scan averaging was used for some comparisons—averaging window 30 min.
- **Adaptive control/timing:** The adaptive scan strategy converged to 90 s scan cycles after a few iterations; based on instantaneous values but constrained by cycle time.
- **Standard error in bins:** Transition between turbine control states can alter standard errors; clearer conditioning by operating status was suggested for the validation plots.
- **Sensors used:** Accelerometer and inclinometer were employed for motion compensation.
- **Averaging for motion compensation:** An adaptive mean over 90 s was used; risk of pseudo-inclinations from transient accelerations was noted.
- **Ambient vs waked TI:** The ambient TI might be better assessed by scanning regions where no wakes are present. However, this approach deviates from the primary goal of the campaign, which is focused on wake measurements. Therefore, the scan pattern is set to 45°–135° relative to the lidar coordinates, ensuring it remains within the wind farm wake.

Relevance to Task 52/WGs: WG6 (nacelle-mounted scanning in offshore RP), WG5 (workflow/metadata).

1.6.5 Motion-corrected FLS turbulence intensity (TI): implications for AEP

Presenter / affiliation: Sam Cressall (Univ. of Edinburgh & Venterra)

Summary: A Monte-Carlo framework (PyWake) propagated TI-measurement errors (raw vs motion-corrected FLS) into AEP P50 and confidence ratios (P90/P50), with reference to DNV-RP-0661, Carbon Trust OWA KPIs, and IEC 61400-50-4.

Conclusion: Corrected TI measurements increase AEP P50 estimates by 0.5-2%, slightly higher than DNV-0661 threshold for the same measurement error. AEP uncertainty from corrected TI increases by 0.2% compared to fixed lidar, noticeable improvement compared to uncorrected TI measurements.

Key scientific points:

- **Methods/results:** Corrected-TI generally leads improve accuracy and tighter confidence; raw-TI can induce larger P50 errors and wider uncertainty. However bias still remains in the AEP when using corrected TI.
- **Caveats:** Thresholds across guidance documents remain heterogeneous; Future work should focus on modelling the FLS specific TI error distributions.

Discussion and clarifications (Q&A excerpts):

Figure 1: Questions placed in the event hall

- **Reference:** One FLS dataset originates from a Fraunhofer buoy (campaign reference “Warren, IWES – FINO3 offshore met mast from March 6, 2024, to August 3, 2024).

Relevance to Task 52/WGs: WG9 (FLS KPIs and acceptance), WG1 (TI from lidar), alignment with IEC 61400-50-4.

1.7 Industry Perspective (13:30–14:45)

The industry session brought together developers, OEMs and technology providers to report on deployment practice, turbulence-intensity (TI) metrics and correction, and progress in long-range scanning systems. Presentations from Shimizu, Nordex, ZX Lidars, Abacus Laser and 2EN highlighted practical validation pathways (mast-based and stand-alone), data-filling challenges for floating systems without nearby references, and the need for bankable uncertainty evaluation linked to specific use-cases. Speakers underscored robust, fatigue-relevant KPIs for TI, ensemble approaches with transparent quality estimation, and stable, precise scanning hardware for near- and far-shore applications. Collectively, the contributions provide near-term inputs to Task 52 working outputs—particularly across WG1, WG5, WG6 and WG9—and help align terminology, QA routines and uncertainty treatment as the Task approaches its final deliverables.

1.8 Breakouts matchmaking & answers to questions captured on the whiteboards

Whiteboards featuring four question, as shown in Figure 1 were placed in the event hall. Each question began with the introductory phrase “What are (your) questions related to wind lidar...” followed by “...to academia,” “...to lidar OEMs,” “...to end-users,” and “...to anyone.”

The answers were recorded as follows:

- **To academia:** feasibility and value of operational 2-D wind-field measurements from lidar.
- **To lidar OEMs:** trajectory for scanning-lidar pricing; transparency on firmware/post-processing changes and their uncertainty implications; range extension beyond 300 m and signal strengthening; prospects for a common data format.
- **To end-users:** required features for DDL control software; best practices for data sharing (incl. open databases); confidence in current inclinometers.
- **To anyone:** timing and scope of stand-alone lidar guidelines; a map of the lidar ecosystem (roles, capabilities, interfaces).

1.9 Various presentations (15:30–17:00)

- [Okan Sargin \(IWES\): Review of WESC 2025 mini-symposium](#)
- [Stefano Letizia \(NREL\): Summary of NAWEA 2024 side event](#)
- [Andrew Black \(Vaisala\): “Simple+” terrain](#)
- [Andy Oldroyd \(Oldbaum\): Lidars and beyond](#)

1.9.1 Okan Sargin (IWES): Review of WESC 2025 mini-symposium

Presenter / affiliation: Okan Sargin / Fraunhofer IWES

Summary: Overview of the WESC 2025 mini-symposium MS01.8 (“Lidars in and out of simulations”), co-organised with Task 57, highlighting recent methods and findings on turbulence estimation, calibration/uncertainty, motion-corrected floating lidar, and single-lidar wind-field reconstruction.

Conclusion: The symposium underscored tangible progress on reducing lidar uncertainty through improved scanning strategies, calibration workflows, motion correction, and reconstruction algorithms, with clear implications for Task 52 deliverables.

Key scientific points:

- **Methods/results:**
 - **Beam orientation effects on turbulence:** VAD showed lower scatter but sensitivity to opening angle; six-beam exhibited higher random error and azimuth-offset dependence.
 - **Calibration & uncertainty:** fibre-optic bench + Monte-Carlo approach reported markedly shorter calibration time and lower combined uncertainty than baseline procedures.
 - **Floating lidar (LES-based evaluation):** motion correction improved recovery of reference TI and wind properties.
 - **Single-Doppler reconstruction (Lagrangian approach):** improved retrievals in non-homogeneous flows relative to VAD.
- **Caveats:** Results are context-specific (methods, sites, stability); broader validation across environments remains necessary. Reader should refer to WESC and individual presentations for details.

Discussion and clarifications (Q&A excerpts):

- No Q&A recorded.

Relevance to Task 52/WGs: WG1, WG9.

1.9.2 Stefano Letizia (NREL): Summary of NAWEA 2024 side event

Presenter / affiliation: Stefano Letizia / NREL

Summary: Synthesis of the NAWEA 2024 Task 52 side event and related U.S./EU field activities, including DOE campaigns (WFIP, AWAKEN, Tall Turbines), offshore barge deployments with scanning/profiling lidars and co-located thermodynamic profiling, and advances in data cleaning (LiDARGO) and ML-based gap-filling.

Conclusion: Coordinated field programmes and open tooling are accelerating robust multi-sensor wind-field characterisation and data usability from turbine to continental scales.

Key scientific points:

- **Methods/results:**
 - **Offshore barge (WFIP3):** one profiling + two scanning lidars; first U.S. offshore co-measurements of wind and atmospheric stability via co-located temperature profiling –
 - **Campaign design:** adaptive scan scheduling using embedded compute (WAGGLE node).
 - **Data workflows:** LiDARGO reduces inconsistencies in scanning-lidar products; public repository available.
 - **ML inpainting:** conditional diffusion models explored for profile gap-filling.
- **Caveats:** Transferability of ML models and cleaning pipelines across instruments/sites needs systematic benchmarking.

Discussion and clarifications (Q&A excerpts):

- Temperature profiling with microwave radiometer was based on black-body emission principles (radiometric retrieval of temperature profiles).

Relevance to Task 52/WGs: WG5, WG6, WG9.

1.9.3 Andrew Black (Vaisala): “Simple+” terrain”

Presenter / affiliation: Andrew Black / Vaisala

Summary: NML-X WG update on the “Simple+” framework for nacelle-mounted lidar (NML) power-performance testing in slightly complex terrain, including pre-test site screening, during-test uncertainty accounting (line-of-sight height mismatch, -exponent sensitivity), DEM guidance, and lidar-based self-consistency checks.

Conclusion: The Simple+ workflow provides a pragmatic route to keep additional terrain-induced NML uncertainty within a 1% budget through upfront screening, explicit zLOS mismatch terms, and sector-wise self-consistency checks.

Key scientific points:

• **Methods/results:**

- Pre-test classification: sector-wise slope and “deviation-from-plane” thresholds extend PPT applicability while controlling uncertainty.
- During-test terms: additional %-uncertainty quantified as a function of $-z_{LOS}-z_{LOS}$ (with Simple+ limit) and ; asymmetry elevates errors; workbook enables propagation.
- Elevation data: lidar point-cloud DEMs (1 m resolution, typically ;1 m elevation uncertainty) preferred to 15–30 m satellite DEMs (1–5 m).
- Self-consistency: sector-to-sector regression (adjacent 2.5D/3.5D ranges) defines an SCP; $|SCP| > 2\%$ triggers a small added term.

- **Caveats:** Applicability offshore and in very flat terrain requires explicit treatment of inflow alignment and elevation reference consistency.

Discussion and clarifications (Q&A excerpts):

- For very flat terrain and offshore contexts, aligning the NML measurements with the inflow was highlighted as an effective means to reduce Type-A uncertainty.
- It was stressed that it is important to quantify elevation-related uncertainty explicitly and avoid unsubstantiated assumptions about “low-uncertainty” DEM

Relevance to Task 52/WGs: WG5, WG8.

1.9.4 Andy Oldroyd (Oldbaum): Lidars and beyond

Presenter / affiliation: Andy Oldroyd / Oldbaum

Summary: Reflective overview of remote-sensing acceptance from early sodar/lidar validation through NORSEWInD, Carbon Trust FLS KPIs, and the IEC 50-X series, identifying current barriers (availability KPIs, TI treatment, short-form test sensitivity) and the need for integrated workflows and integrated calibration.

Conclusion: Market confidence hinges on harmonised uncertainty frameworks and fully integrated calibration/testing protocols, ideally considering multi-sensor (e.g., lidar + microwave radiometer (MWR)) workflows.

Key scientific points:

• **Methods/results:**

- **Historical protocols:** progression from tall-mast correlation tests to structured stage/type qualifications and KPI frameworks (e.g., Carbon Trust for FLS).
- **Standards:** incorporation of lidar within IEC 50-X underscores uncertainty as the justification for campaigns; terminology must be normalised.
- **Forward look:** integration of wind lidars with microwave radiometers for stability/ABL metrics; emerging programmes targeting MWR on floating platforms.

- **Caveats:** Several “excellent concepts” in standards require more test-driven evidence, especially for short-form testing sensitivity, EOC EV and uncertainty assessment.

Discussion and clarifications (Q&A excerpts):

- Comment noted: the community needs to “fully integrate calibration testing” across workflows.

Relevance to Task 52/WGs: WG5, WG6, WG9

2 Day 2: Wednesday 24 September 2025

Day 2 opened with an agenda overview by the Operating Agent (OA), before moving into an OEM-focused session combining brief presentations and a panel discussion on current challenges and further opportunities, with contributions from Leice (Lili Jia), Movelaser (Liu Zhixin), Vaisala (Frédéric Delbos), ZX Lidars (Matthew Smith), and Pavana (Annika Baltzer). Panel discussion was chaired by OA.

The meeting was concluded with a few general notes and instructions how to get involved. The IEA Wind Task 52 Operating Agent can be contacted via IEAWind.Task52@iwes.fraunhofer.de, and the task is also present on LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/4037465> or search for “IEA Wind Task 52”). Interested participants should become a (formal) Task 52 participant to join an already active working group, or propose future webinars and/or workshops.

2.1 Agenda - Day 2

Time	Activity
09:00	Presentations + panel: OEMs on challenges (and further opportunities) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lili Jia (Leice) • Liu Zhixin (Movelaser) • Frédéric Delbos (Vaisala) • Matthew Smith (ZX Lidars) • Annika Baltzer (Pavana)
10:30	Coffee, Tea
10:45	How far did we get? What's next? Followed by brainstorming and breakouts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alexander Stoekl (Energiewerkstatt): Results of complex terrain working group • Short inputs on digitalization and collaboration with Task 43, TEM 111 and link to Task 52, liaison with IEC
12:15	Summary / Wrap-up
12:45	Lunch
13:30	Workshops <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cold Climate - WG lead Sara Koller • TI - WG lead Richard Frühmann
16:30	End of general meeting

Table 3: Agenda of Day 2.

2.2 Presentations + panel: OEMs on challenges (and further opportunities)

The short summaries below distil the key points from each OEM’s presentation—Leice, Movelaser,

Figure 2: OEM Panel

Vaisala, ZX Lidars and Pavana (test-site owner, not an OEM)—drawn exclusively from the presentations and intended to frame the subsequent panel discussion.

Leice (Lili Jia) – Leice outlined a portfolio spanning vertical profilers, floating lidar and dual-scanning lidar (DSL), with a stated strength in assimilating high-resolution lidar data into WRF for hyper-local assessment and forecasting. The DSL concept targets near-/offshore sites (suggested within ~ 10 km from shore and >200 m water depth), offering PPI mapping of wakes/turbulence and arguing reduced permitting effort versus buoy deployments. The slides emphasise the need for standards, independent benchmarking and interoperable formats to make DSL bankable and integrable with SCADA and control.

Movelaser (Liu Zhixin) – Movelaser positions its range as addressing accuracy, portability, cost efficiency and reliability, citing UL/DNV/DTU verifications/classifications and high-volume manufacturing to reduce cost barriers. Case studies show data availability in harsh environments (dust, fog/rain, high altitude, low temperature), with examples of >90–95% availability at many heights and noted limitations at low levels under heavy snowfall. The deck calls for standardisation, complex-terrain/offshore methods and seamless integration with digitalisation/AI to accelerate adoption.

Vaisala (Frédéric Delbos) – The WindCube® 2.1 XP is presented as providing full-profile measurements (20 heights) up to ~ 400 m with higher availability, lower uncertainty and a connected workflow via the Compass cloud. The slides frame remaining challenges around turbulence-intensity standards, the fidelity of lidar-derived TI, and measurement in complex terrain.

ZX Lidars (Matthew Smith) – ZX reports IEC-method

classifications for the ZX 300e from 21–200 m, reporting a final accuracy class and standard classification uncertainty of 0% at those heights, alongside eliminating CW directional ambiguity with direction accuracy within $\pm 0.5^\circ$. The presentation introduces “METICE”, an ANN-based approach for cup-equivalent TI evaluated across >17 sites, and a “Midar” configuration that uses a verified lidar on a 91 m mast to extend traceability for ground-based verifications toward ~ 300 m; more high-quality mast datasets are requested.

Pavana (Annika Baltzer) – As an accredited laboratory, Pavana describes its role linking manufacturers and practical deployment, highlighting a 200 m verification site at Janneby with 10 instrumented heights and parallel lidar pads used for device benchmarking. The deck argues for clearer guidance enabling stand-alone lidar sufficiency, increasing data availability, applying deep-learning QC, and intensifying cooperation with OEMs and standards bodies.

Figure 3: Breakout sessions

2.3 Results of complex terrain working group and “What’s next”

After the morning break, the meeting turned to “How far did we get / what’s next?”, including the conclusion “Complex Terrain Working Group” update by Alexander Stökl (Energiewerkstatt) and short inputs on digitalisation, collaboration with Task 43, TEM 111, and liaison with IEC.

Presenter / affiliation: Dr Alexander Stökl / Energiewerkstatt Verein

Summary: WG3 reported a verification study of ground-based vertical-profiling lidar in complex terrain, assembling 83 lidar–met–mast datasets from 50 sites and applying shared tools for terrain characterisation and LiDAR–mast comparison to assess direction- and curvature-dependent errors.

Conclusion: Stochastic errors are broadly similar in simple and complex terrain; mean wind-speed errors vary with wind direction and correlate with terrain curvature. A guideline on applying ground-based lidar in complex terrain is in preparation for publication in late 2025.

Key scientific points:

- **Methods/results:**
 - Distributed Windows terrain-evaluation executable and Excel/VBA comparison sheet enabled partner-side processing; subsequent 5H analyses show low curvature–error correlation (approximately 0.42–0.48) and direction-dependent bias.
- **Caveats:** Outliers likely stem from forested sites, short reference heights, large lidar–mast separations, high TSI, and sparse bins; directional binning is required—single integral metrics are inadequate.

Discussion and clarifications (Q&A excerpts):

- It was suggested that a differentiation could be made between different LiDAR models, opening angles and measurement principles, which was noted and will be considered within the report.

Relevance to Task 52/WGs: WG3 (Complex Terrain), with links to WG1 and WG5.

2.4 Breakouts

Participants worked in five groups during a one-hour breakout to capture priorities for the lidar community and Task 52 beyond 2025. The exercise combined an open whiteboard of cross-cutting questions with group work on topics for a potential Phase 2, concrete deliverables, and preferred engagement formats. The notes below synthesise the flip-chart outputs without attribution.

Each group worked against four guiding prompts:

1. What are your topics for a possible Phase 2 of Task 52 (and why)?
2. What would be a relevant deliverable (and what approach to achieve it)?
3. What workshops (within Task 52) would you suggest / be interested in?
4. What other formats (side events at conferences, online lunch seminars etc.) would you like to see / attend / support with your contributions?

2.4.1 Topics proposed for a possible Phase 2 of Task 52

- **Control & calibration:** Lidar-Assisted Control; faster, traceable calibration of nacelle lidars (months → weeks); calibration approaches combining LOS and

WFR; concurrent comparisons of commercial systems; practical pathways to simplify and expedite calibration raised by several groups.

- **Turbulence & complex flow:** Robust TI characterisation (incl. complex terrain and long-range scanning); extreme winds/gusts; propagation of TI and related errors through workflows; consistent treatment of UNC-LOS-WFR. Proposal to explore a “Turbulence Universal Translator (TUT)” concept to align metrics across applications.
- **Measurement reach & availability:** Taller heights, extended range (incl. >300 m feasibility); balancing data quality vs. availability under varying atmospheric conditions.
- **Applications & physics:** Wake quantification (incl. noise/ecological aspects); short-term forecasting; tower vibration modes; adding temperature and other state variables.
- **New platforms & methods:** UAS/drone-based or spinning platforms; ML for reconstruction/QA/QC; workflow links from parameters → decisions (boundary layer, clouds, waves, stability, shear/veer).
- **Standards & ecosystem:** Acceptance criteria and KPIs; coherence across lidar standards (IEC/IEA alignment); clarification of ISARS status and scope; continuity of WG9 (FLS); stronger developer-OEM feedback loops.

2.4.2 Candidate deliverables and approaches

- **Recommended practices & guidance:** RP for Scanning Lidar (uncertainty quantification, value-add pathways); stand-alone lidar guidance, including site suitability aspects; white paper on key use-cases aggregating developer needs and evidence.
- **Uncertainty & harmonisation:** Procedures to simplify/accelerate calibration and reduce time-to-measurement; synchronised methods, common language/terminology, and uncertainty budgets consistent with IEC; clarity on point vs. volume measurements; explicit TI error-propagation recipes.
- **Knowledge assets:** State-of-the-art review; ecosystem map of actors, workflows and interfaces; semantic glossary/common language; guidance on data licences and sharing models.
- **Benchmarking & transparency:** Round-robin/detection exercises; open verification database; TI-oriented deliverables (definitions, KPIs, exemplars); transparent handling of algorithm/firmware revisions; increased IEC-IEA exchange.
- **Bankability interface:** Investor’s/financier’s handbook addressing how lidar evidence reduces uncertainty and risk; targeted engagement with development banks, noting reports that some do not currently accept lidar-based evidence.

2.4.3 Workshops and other engagement formats requested

- **Targeted workshops:** Joint sessions between project developers and turbine OEMs; methods & stat-

istics; case-study reviews (including successes and failures); links to finance/bankability; deeper engagement with meteorology/atmospheric science.

- **Participation model:** Clear framing of Task operating modes and how to contribute; bring more developers into workshops; strategies to secure manufacturer participation.
- **Ongoing forums:** Online half-day events; more frequent Lunch Seminars; identification of external events for Task 52 contributions.

2.4.4 Observations and next steps (from the room)

- There is broad alignment on advancing research on TI, scanning-lidar uncertainty, and faster calibration to the next level, while keeping availability and range practical (incl. beyond 300 m where feasible).
- Multiple groups called for coherent KPIs, common data formats, clear data-licensing guidance, and a transparent treatment of algorithm/firmware revisions.
- The community wishes to maintain momentum on WG9 (FLS) and to embed open data/verification elements across themes.
- A stronger interface with developers and with development-finance institutions is seen as necessary to improve acceptance and deployment.

These notes are intended to inform the scoping of a potential Phase 2 and the final-year outputs of Task 52, including updates to working-group roadmaps, Recommended Practices drafts, and dissemination plans.

2.5 Workshops

The afternoon comprised parallel workshops on Cold Climate (led by Sara Koller) and Turbulence Intensity (led by Richard Frühmann), followed by a brief wrap-up to consolidate the day’s outputs for the final Task year.

2.5.1 Progress report from the TI working group

Over the last year, the TI working group has reviewed the current state-of-the art on lidar derived TI through gathering knowledge articles on the topic and inviting speakers from research and industry to share their experiences. Topics included the measurement of TI using lidars, correction approaches to better match cup derived TI and use cases in which the measured TI values are applied in the context of wind energy engineering. During the workshop, the group met in person to decide how to structure the work in the remaining period, and define a scope for the final deliverable.

The use of TI for assessing the design loads for a wind turbine was identified as the most urgent use case for the wind energy industry. One of the main challenges is to assess how the TI measured by a particular lidar type (maybe in combination with a correction algorithm) compares with TI measured by a cup or sonic anemometer. The group therefore agreed to focus their effort on defining suitable methods for mak-

ing such a comparison, as well as a frame work for assessing the range of conditions under which the results of a comparison can be applied to a measurement campaign. The conclusions will be presented in a final report in Q2 2026.

3 Summary

The IEA Wind Task 52 general meeting was held over two days, on September 23-24, 2025, in Kassel. The event brought together a diverse group of stakeholders, including wind lidar researchers, lidar OEMs, wind farm developers, turbine OEMs, and certification bodies. The aim was to explore how to facilitate the large-scale deployment of wind lidar technology in the wind industry.

The first day of the General Meeting, held on Tuesday, 23 September 2025, concentrated on provided detailed updates on the progress of each working group, reflecting on their respective challenges and achievements.

Day 1 began with the Operating Agent, Julia Gottschall, setting the context for the final year of Task 52 by tracing the evolution from Task 32's focus on single-lidar technology to Task 52's broader remit around multiple lidars, user evidence and standardisation, and by stressing that 2025-26 activities must converge on citable, end-of-Phase-1 outputs such as expert notes, Recommended Practices inputs and datasets. After a welcome from the host institute Fraunhofer IEE and guidance on the overall timeline and possible Phase 2, the morning continued with high-level status updates from the working groups on turbulence intensity, cold climate, digitalisation, scanning lidar and floating lidar, followed by an academic session that showcased new methods for offshore scanning-lidar alignment, multi-lidar coherence measurements, the evolution of research scanning systems, nacelle-scanning wake measurements and the impact of turbulence-intensity measurement uncertainty on AEP. In the afternoon, an industry session brought together Shimizu, Nordex, ZX Lidars, Abacus Laser and 2EN to discuss deployment practice, turbulence-intensity KPIs and correction strategies, the challenges of data filling for floating systems and the need for bankable uncertainty evaluation, after which participants contributed to matchmaking breakouts via whiteboards that collected questions to academia, OEMs, end-users and the wider community. The day closed with additional presentations on the WESC 2025 mini-symposium, the NAWEA 2024 side event, the "Simple+" framework for nacelle-mounted lidar in slightly complex terrain and broader "lidars and beyond" topics, before a short wrap-up of Day 1.

Day 2 opened with an agenda overview from the Operating Agent and moved directly into an OEM-focused session in which Leice, Movelaser, Vaisala, ZX Lidars and Pavana outlined their portfolios

Figure 4: Group picture

and emphasised topics such as dual-scanning concepts for near- and offshore sites, data availability in harsh environments, remaining gaps around lidar-derived turbulence-intensity standards and complex terrain, and the need for standardisation, interoperable formats, independent benchmarking and stronger links to digitalisation and AI. After the break, the plenary turned to the question "How far did we get, and what is next?", with a detailed update from the complex-terrain working group reporting on a large verification study of ground-based vertical-profiling lidar in complex terrain. In a subsequent one-hour breakout, five groups worked against common prompts to identify candidate topics for a possible Phase 2 (including control and calibration, turbulence and complex flow, measurement reach and availability, new platforms and methods, and standards and ecosystem issues), to propose concrete deliverables such as scanning-lidar Recommended Practices, stand-alone lidar guidance, harmonised uncertainty procedures and investor-facing material on lidar bankability, and to suggest future engagement formats ranging from targeted workshops to more frequent online seminars. The afternoon was dedicated to parallel workshops on cold climate and turbulence intensity, led by the respective working-group leads, which consolidated technical priorities and open questions for the final Task-year outputs before the meeting concluded with a brief wrap-up and an invitation for interested stakeholders to join Task 52 formally or help shape future webinars and workshops.

Task 52 welcomes anyone interested in working together on research to make wind lidar the best and preferred wind measurement tool for wind energy applications. Please see iea-wind.org/task52/ for details.

List of Participants

The following table lists people who attended part or all of the meeting. The presence of a person's name or company name in this list should not be taken to imply that a person or their employer agrees with any of the opinions set out in these minutes.

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